

Physical validation of ODYSSEE Nuclear Code System

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ABSTRACT

ODYSSEE, the new EDF and Framatome nuclear code system, was extensively validated against a large set of measurements including critical mock-ups, spent-fuel analysis, experimental facilities, power reactors operation and international benchmarks. All the Verification and Validation process follow French Safety Authority Reference Guide n°28. The main ODYSSEE validation results are presented. Specific validation results are given for CARABAS-APOLLO2 lattice code, COCAGNE core code, core thermal hydraulic (TH) THYC code and ATHENA multi-physics coupler, focusing on safety analysis and accuracy for next PWR generation.

Keywords: neutronics, core thermal-hydraulics, multi-physics coupling, validation

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper we present the Verification and Validation (V&V) of ODYSSEE, the new EDF and Framatome Nuclear Code System. ODYSSEE is based on CARABAS-APOLLO2 lattice code, COCAGNE (3D SPN and SN core solvers) core code, core thermal hydraulic (TH) THYC code and ATHENA multi-physics coupler, whose models are described in detail in a separate paper [1]. The V&V process is crucial for allowing code reliability. In this context, ODYSSEE Nuclear Code System undergoes rigorous testing, including comparison with experimental data and comparison with reference codes through benchmarking, to ensure its accuracy and reliability in nuclear reactor modeling. The V&V process allows to qualify the code system in a validity domain and ensures its robustness for industrial applications. In the French context, EDF recently submitted a Qualification File to the ASN (Autorité de Sûreté Nucléaire et Radioprotection) to use ODYSSEE for safety applications. The ASN defines the VVUQ (Verification Validation and Uncertainties Quantification) framework for such complex process in its Guide n°28 [2].

2. NEUTRONIC VALIDATION

The validation of ODYSSEE for neutronics is based on a two-steps approach, covering a large application range, by comparison, for each step, with Monte-Carlo reference codes and measured data:

- validation of the fuel assembly transport code CARABAS (from assembly to 2D core level),
- validation of the CARABAS-COCAGNE chained system (from assembly to 3D core level).

Only a short selection and highlights of validation results is described and illustrated in this paper.

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2.1. Fuel assembly transport code validation

The validation of the fuel assembly transport code CARABAS is based on:

- comparisons with Monte-Carlo codes (MCNP5, TRIPOLI4, SERPENT2, using the same JEFF3.1.1 nuclear data library) on a large set of different assemblies (and 2D large cores), on fresh fuel and in evolution, on reactivity, pin by pin fission rates, control rods worth, Gd pins worth, boron worth, moderator coefficient, temperature coefficient and kinetics parameters.
- comparisons with experimental data measured on small critical cores (performed in France (as in CEA EOLE facility), Belgium, Brazil or the USA), on reactivity, pin by pin fission rates (illustrated in Figure 1), isothermal coefficient, void coefficient, control rods worth, Gd pins worth, kinetics parameters, gamma heating (EPRI experiment), and comparisons with isotopic composition measurements of spent UOX, MOX (illustrated in Figure 2), ERU (Enriched Reprocessed Uranium) and Gd fuel sample irradiated in power reactors (in France, Belgium or Switzerland).

Figure 1. RMS of C/M-1 comparisons (%) on fission rates between CARABAS and critical experiments

Figure 2. Comparisons between CARABAS and measurements (from post-irradiation analysis) on the isotopic composition of different spent fuel samples from power reactors, at various burnup (C/M-1 in %, UOX samples on the left, MOX samples on the right)

2.2. Core code validation

The validation of the CARABAS-COCAGNE chain at the core level is based on:

- comparisons COCAGNE vs CARABAS, on a large set of infinite medium assemblies, 2x2, 3x3, 5x5 assembly clusters, and on 2D large cores (illustrated in Figure 3), on the following parameters: reactivity, pin by pin power distribution, kinetics parameters and detector response.

Figure 3. Comparisons between COCAGNE and CARABAS on various 2x2, 3x3 and 5x5 assembly clusters (left) and a 2D core (right) on the pin-by-pin power (in %)

- comparisons with TRIPOLI4 Monte-Carlo code on 3D cores, on a large set of core loading patterns, on the following parameters: reactivity, power distribution, kinetics parameters.
- comparisons with experimental data measured on power cores:
 - o on the French EDF fleet (on approximately 800 cycles for the fuel managements currently in operation) and on the EPR in operation worldwide. On one hand, zero power physics startup tests: critical boron concentration, isothermal coefficient, rod cluster worth, boron differential worth. On the other hand, physics tests at power: critical boron concentration (illustrated in Figure 4) and power distributions (illustrated on 2D radial power distribution in Figure 5, and on the Axial Power Offset in Figure 6).
 - o on special tests performed on the French EDF fleet: on dissymmetrical configurations, at low temperature and pressure, on zero power physics startup tests performed at advanced burnup on some cycles.
 - o on international benchmarks: BEAVRS and Watts Bar 1 [3] benchmarks.
 - o on transient cases such as normal operation transients (for instance power escalations), rod drop tests, Doppler tests (based on the analysis of the impact on the core power of a power variation imposed on the turbine), SPERT III-E experimental rod ejection transients (illustrated in Figure 7 for HFP-86 case).

Such large set of comparisons are used to evaluate ODYSSEE uncertainties, for each parameter of interest:

- for critical boron concentration, moderator coefficient, rod and boron differential worths: based on a statistical analysis of the available comparisons to measurements on operating cores
- for reactivity, kinetics parameters, Doppler coefficients and power distributions: based on the various code to code and code to measurements available comparisons.

Figure 4. ODYSSEE results vs measurements on Critical Boron Concentration at core power > 95% as a function of cycle burnup (C-M, in ppm)

Figure 5. ODYSSEE results vs measurements on the maximum absolute discrepancy on 2D radial power distribution for assemblies with relative power > 0,9 and core power > 95%, as a function of cycle burnup (M/C-1, in %)

Figure 6. ODYSSEE results vs measurements on the Axial Offset at core power > 95%, as a function of cycle burnup (C-M, in %)

Figure 7. ODYSSEE results vs measurements on the core power (in MW) along HFP-86 SPERT III-E rod ejection case (in MW, COCAGNE results in blue, measurements in red)

These elements demonstrate the good quality of the physical models of the chain and the validation of its use for industrial usages, within a defined application range.

3. CORE THERMAL HYDRAULIC VALIDATION

THYC is ODYSSEE's 3D thermal hydraulics code whose models for industrial applications are described in a separate paper [1]. The validation of these models and the extension of their domain of use (flow redistributions due to buoyancy forces, high void fractions and transient calculations) was performed based on a wide experimental database and is described in this section. Overall, THYC physical models demonstrate good accuracy across all available experiments and hence are considered able to evaluate precisely enough local core TH conditions on a wide range of operating conditions. In the following

sections, validation elements are outlined according to specific industrial application domains and the dominant physical phenomena.

3.1. Evaluation of Departure from Nucleate Boiling Ratio (DNBR) margins

Under abnormal PWR core operating conditions with two-phase flow, TH quantities, particularly vapor quality, are very different at core center with respect to core periphery. Flow redistributions will occur, from the most powerful fuel assemblies to the less powerful ones. As the most powerful assemblies receive less flow, the increase in quality will be more significant, leading to decrease in the DNBR margin. Therefore, the redistribution of flow between assemblies (or subchannels) is the dominant phenomenon in the core. In the subchannel approach, the axial pressure drop must be accurately modeled and validated against experimental data. This ensures that the code can reliably predict, under given core conditions, the axial pressure gradient differentials between fuel assemblies operating at different power levels, along with the resulting flow redistribution effects.

3.1.1. Axial pressure drop models

The validation approach, focusing on the combination of pressure loss and wall friction closure laws for single and two-phase flows, aims to validate the modeling of the axial pressure drop by using differential pressure measurements within critical heat flux experiments on 5×5 rod bundle with mixing grids. The experimental profile is accurately predicted by the code, where the location of the mixing grids is clearly visible, as illustrated in Figure 8, based on an experiment representative of typical PWR operating conditions.

Figure 8. Axial evolutions of calculated vs. measured pressure drops for a two-phase test

3.1.2. Non-equilibrium closure laws

The amount of steam generated within the coolant directly influences neutron moderation, thereby affecting both the reactivity feedback and the rod power. However, void formation also affects the axial pressure drop, which in turn influences the crossflows between subchannels. It is therefore necessary to assess THYC's ability to predict the amount of void generated and its radial distribution within a bundle, as well as to validate the non-equilibrium closure laws (drift flux and subcooled boiling models), which play a critical role in the system's overall behavior. For this purpose, the PSBT experiments (PWR Subchannel and Bundle Tests [4]), performed with water-steam mixtures on the NUPEC PWR loop (Nuclear Power Engineering Corporation, Japan) under both steady-state and transient conditions, are analyzed. Figure 9 displays comparisons between the simulated and measured void fractions. These experimental campaigns, conducted under extensive and fully representative conditions of PWR operation, explore several configurations of 5×5 fuel lattices with mixing grids. These are an internationally recognized standard for the validation of PWR core TH codes. Configurations representing isolated subchannels were also investigated (Figure 9), which allowed for the decoupling

of turbulent diffusion phenomena. THYC results are highly satisfactory and align well with the current state-of-the-art in existing TH codes.

Figure 9. Calculated void fractions vs. measured ones on PSBT tests (bundle and subchannel).

3.2. Validation for the special case of cooling accidents initiated at zero power

Among the postulated abnormal transients, the Main Steam Line Break (MSLB) is characterized by a strongly asymmetric behavior in the reactor core and low flow conditions following the shutdown of the primary pumps. Thus, buoyancy-affected flows may occur in the differentially heated core rod bundle at low flow rate. To validate THYC in such conditions, the Battelle experimental campaign, conducted at the PNNL test facility provides a relevant reference [5]. The setup consists of an electrically heated 2x6 rod bundle subjected to lateral power skews and enclosed in a rectangular flow housing. The experiments notably investigated flow redistributions driven by buoyancy forces, including lateral crossflows and thermal plumes, under mixed convection regimes.

The validation approach is based on an up-scaling approach. Large Eddy Simulations (LES) are first performed using CFD code *code_saturne* [6]. The simulation results are compared against local measurements, showing good agreement with the main trends. Subsequently, a benchmark is carried out between these validated LES results, averaged over the subchannel surface, and the predictions by THYC. Further details on these simulations can be found in ref. [7].

Regarding mixed convection flows, THYC successfully captures the main flow features, including redistribution patterns and thermal plumes (Figure 10). The results show a satisfactory agreement with *code_saturne*, which is used as the reference for this comparison.

Figure 10. Subchannel average axial velocity U_z normalized by the bulk velocity U_b (left) and temperature (right) profiles at the top of a differentially heated rod bundle, predicted by a wall-resolved LES calculation using `code_saturne` (CS) and using THYC.

4. MULTIPHYSICS COUPLING VALIDATION

The multiphysics code coupling is performed using the ATHENA coupler which embeds the data transfer functions and mesh projecting tools among the main codes (COGAGNE, THYC and CATHARE3 [8]) as well as the time step and convergence management. ATHENA is described in a separate paper [1].

The validation of ATHENA is based on comparison with experimental data and code-to-code benchmarks. These validation results are only partially described here, with a focus on the simulation of a load rejection transient on a French 4-loop 1300 MWe PWR.

The experimental dataset includes time evolution of core power and axial power offset, control rods positions, cold and hot legs temperatures, steam generator pressure and steam mass flow rate.

The simulation has been carried out by coupling COGAGNE with system TH code CATHARE3 via the ATHENA coupler. Both the primary and secondary circuits are explicitly modeled with CATHARE3 except for the turbogenerator and the condenser. The core is made of 193 fuel assemblies modeled with 193 axial elements in CATHARE3, each of them receiving a thermal power profile computed by COGAGNE.

Figure 11. Simulated vs. measured axial power offset (left) and control rods position (right)

The following parameters are imposed as boundary conditions for the transient, based on the values recorded by sensors: initial power level, initial control rods position, both initial pressurizer pressure and

level, speed of the primary pumps, Chemical and Volumetric Control System (CVCS) loading / unloading flow rates, feedwater temperature of the 4 steam generators, loading temperature (downstream of the heat exchanger). Figure 11 displays a good agreement between measured and calculated results on both the axial power offset and control rods positions. While the control rods positions at $t=0$ are imposed, their positions throughout the whole transient are successfully predicted as well as axial power offset. After 80 s, differences between computed and measured axial power offset (less than 2.5 %) are due to discrepancies in the temperature-regulation rod groups. These results show that the effect on the core of a perturbation on the secondary loop is accurately predicted by ATHENA coupler.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper gives an overview of the main verification and validation results obtained with ODYSSEE. All validation results based on experimental data and/or code-to-code benchmarks demonstrate the accuracy of the comparisons and ODYSSEE's high predictivity level in simulating a large PWR core features and operating domain. ODYSSEE predictivity enables to use it for safety analysis of the next PWR generation (both large reactors and Small Modular Reactors) as well as for new fuel managements.

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